

EFFECT OF THE POLICY OF FUEL SUBSIDY REMOVAL ON LIVELIHOOD IN DUTSIN-MA, NIGERIA: IMPLICATIONS ON QUALITY OF LIFE OF HOUSEHOLDS

By

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ABSTRACT

The policy of fuel subsidy removal has the capacity to improve livelihood that can improve the quality of life of households if the resources are utilized efficiently. The removal of subsidy is expected to improve social and economic welfare of households if the funds are channeled appropriately. Yet there seems to be a mismatch between the incomes gotten, which may not be able to stimulate spending to boost economic activities of households in Dutsin-Ma. This paper investigated the effect of removal of fuel subsidy on the livelihood of households. The study employed survey method for data collection. Questionnaire was administered for a sample of 391 respondents across the four wards in the study area, which include Dutsin-Ma A, Dutsin-Ma B, Shema and Dabawa. The theoretical framework used is a synthesis of classical demand theory and income and substitution effect theory. The analytical technique employed for this study was descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The study found that the removal of fuel subsidy has affected negatively the source of income of 80.6% households, only 80.1% of households received welfare support to improve their income level, 51.9% received grant below ₦40,000 to cushion the effect of subsidy removal. Inferential statistics was used to test for hypothesis using the chi-square technique. The chi-square calculated (χ^2_c) value was 85.13 and tabulated (χ^2_t) was 14.44. This paper concluded that removal of fuel subsidy have effect on the livelihood of households hence affecting the quality of life which has prevented them from accessing certain basic life sustenance indices to improve standard of living.

Key words: Fuel Subsidy, Fuel Subsidy Removal, Livelihood, Welfare, Quality of Life,
JEL Classification code: H5, H53, I3, I38

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The policy of fuel subsidy removal has the capacity to improve livelihood and quality of life of households if the resources are utilized efficiently. The removal of subsidy is expected

to improve social and economic welfare of households if the funds are channeled appropriately. The removal of fuel subsidies is a globally debated issue, primarily because of its direct and indirect effects on the social and economic stability of households. The removal of fuel subsidies is a policy decision that has generated widespread academic and policy interest due to its profound implications for household livelihoods, particularly in developing countries. Subsidies have historically been used as tools to cushion households against volatile fuel prices and to stimulate economic activity by reducing the cost of transportation and energy-intensive goods and services.

Fuel subsidies are financial aids provided by government so as to keep fuel prices below market levels, have long been employed in both developed and developing countries to cushion the impact of volatile global oil prices on citizens. Dutsin-Ma is predominantly agrarian, the effects of subsidy removal are compounded by existing economic challenges such as poverty, unemployment, and inflation. Dustin-Ma Local Government Area. Households depend on subsistence farming, petty trading, and informal labor, are particularly vulnerable to changes in energy costs. Higher fuel prices translate directly into increased costs for transportation and agricultural inputs such as fertilizers and mechanized equipment, leading to reduced productivity and profitability for farmers (Omorogiuwa et al., 2014).

Given the multidimensional effects of fuel subsidy removal, it is imperative to analyze its effects on the livelihood of households in Dustin-Ma Local Government Area. This study seeks to explore socioeconomic consequences of this policy change, including its implications for household welfare, income generation, and access to essential services that can improve the quality of life. This paper seeks to focus on the immediate and long-term socioeconomic effects of fuel subsidy removal on households in Dustin-Ma Local Government Area.

Policy: refers to a set of principles, guidelines and actions that can be implemented by the government to achieve certain goals to address certain issues in the economy. These policies are designed to solve challenges in the economy such public safety, governance social welfare and economic development

Fuel subsidy: Fuel subsidy refers to a financial assistance mechanism provided by the government to reduce the cost of fuel for consumers by setting prices below market levels.

Fuel subsidy removal: Fuel subsidy removal is the elimination of government financial support instead of reducing fuel prices, leading to fuel prices being determined by market forces. In this study, fuel subsidy removal pertains to the 2023 policy decision by the Nigerian government to discontinue the provision of subsidies on petroleum products.

Livelihood: Household livelihoods refer to the means and resources by which households secure the necessities of life, including food, shelter, education, healthcare, and income. For this study, household livelihoods encompass the various strategies, activities, and assets utilized by families in Dustin-Ma Local Government Area of Katsina State to sustain their economic and social well-being.

Quality of life: Quality of life is a subjective measure of well-being, encompassing an individual's perception of their position in life, considering their culture, values, goals, expectations, standards, and concerns. It's not just about material possessions or living conditions, but also includes factors like health, relationships, and personal fulfillment

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.2 Theoretical Literature

Income and Substitution Effects Theory

The notion of Income and Substitution Effects is frequently associated with the scholarly contributions of Sir John Hicks. In 1934, Hicks, a distinguished economist from Britain, formulated the Hicksian decomposition of the price effect, which effectively disentangled it into two distinct components: The Income Effect and the Substitution Effect. The income effect describes how a change in the price of a good affects the consumer's real purchasing power, influencing their demand for that good. When the price of a good decreases, the consumer's real income effectively increases because they can now afford more of the good or other goods with the same amount of money. For normal goods, this increase in purchasing power leads to an increase in the quantity demanded. Conversely, for inferior goods, a higher real income might reduce demand since consumers may opt for more desirable alternatives. The income effect illustrates that changes in real income, due to price variations, directly affect consumer choices and overall consumption. The substitution effect occurs when a change in the price of a good alters its relative cost compared to other goods, prompting consumers to adjust their consumption patterns. When the price of a good decreases, it becomes relatively cheaper than its substitutes, leading consumers to buy more of the cheaper good and less of its substitutes (Pindyck & Rubinfeld, 2018). The substitution effect is always negative; that is, when the price of a good falls, the quantity demanded of the good increases because consumers shift from relatively more expensive alternatives to the now cheaper option.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Several literature were reviewed on partial oil subsidy removal, removal of fuel subsidies, socioeconomic effects of subsidy, Fuel Subsidy Removal on Low-Income Earners etc. For instance, the study of Akerele (2024), Datti (2024), Ezuem and Agada (2024), Evans, Nwaogwugwu, Vincent and Ojanipawa (2023), conducted a study titled "Effects of Partial Oil Subsidy Removal on Livelihood Activities of Rural Populace in Yewa Division of Ogun State, Nigeria." examined how the removal of fuel subsidies influenced household spending in urban areas of Northwest Nigeria, explored the effects of fuel subsidy removal on living standards in Taraba State. examined the removal of fuel subsidies and found that it led to a marked increase in the cost of living, disproportionately affecting low-income households.

Mohammed, Khalifa and Abubakar (2024), Effect of petrol subsidy removal on government income, cost of living, consumption patterns, savings and investment, and SMEs performance Wazakari and Tammi (2024), Ali, Ahmad, and Jibrilla (2024), and Sheyin, A. O. (2018). They explored the socio-economic effects of oil subsidy removal on resettled households in Adamawa North Senatorial District, Nigeria, the socio-economic consequences of subsidy removal on households in Adamawa State, Nigeria and The Effects of Subsidy Removal on the Escalation of Political Corruption in Nigeria. Furthermore, Umar and Mohd Nor's (2024), Agboje (2024), Ismaila and Hassan (2024), Onyambayi, Abdullahi, Alogwuja, Adejo, and Esthe, Meludu, Komolafe, and Chilaka (2023), Juochi (2024), research titled "The Assessment of Impacts of 2016 Fuel Subsidy Removal on Low-Income Earners in Katsina Metropolis, Nigeria, Agboje (2024), Oladimeji and Umar (2024), Impact of Fuel Subsidy Removal on Vulnerable Households in Zamfara State. Examined the impact of fuel subsidy

removal on poverty levels across Nigeria. investigated the effects of fuel subsidy removal on the prices of major food commodities in Southeastern Nigeria. Investigated perceptions of fuel subsidy removal among farming households in Imo State. assessed the effects of subsidy removal on Nigeria's working class, finding that the policy led to increased living costs.

Although the study of Okereke et al. (2024), Ogwuche, Adejor, Dabish, Garba, and Dole (2024), employed the Quadratic Almost Ideal Demand System (QUAIDS) model to examine Nigerian households' energy consumption, examined the impact of subsidy removal on Nigeria's economic growth using a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). Ozili (2023) extended this discourse through a detailed analysis of both macroeconomic and microeconomic effects stemming from the 2023 fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria. Yunusa, Yakubu, Emeje, Ibrahim, Stephen, and Egbunu (2023) reviewed secondary materials to assess the rationale behind Nigeria's subsidy removal and its socio-economic consequences. Their content analysis indicated that while the policy aimed to boost economic growth and attract investments.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Cross-Sectional Survey

The cross sectional survey was adopted for this study.

3.2 Sample Size of the Study

The study area for the research is Dutsin-Ma local government area of Katsina State Nigeria. The population size in Dutsin-Ma as at 2006 is 169, 829 and projected population size is from 2006 for 2022 is 303, 500 (National Bureau of Statistics and National Population Commission, 2006). The study used the projected population size for the year 2022. The computation below is a representation of the sample size taken for this research from the population using the Yaro and Yamane's formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = Total Population

e = Level of Significance (0.05)

Therefore;

$$n = \frac{303500}{1 + 600(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{303500}{1 + 303500(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{303500}{1 + 178.75}$$

$$n = \frac{600}{399.47} \quad n = 399.47$$

3.3 Sampling Technique

Multi-stage sampling technique was employed for the study population. Purposive sampling was used to distribute the questionnaire because the respondents were identified and known. Five ward areas were sampled systematically.

3.4 Analytical Technique

The study adopted descriptive statistics by use of frequency distribution, percentages and secondly it employed inferential statistics by using the chi-square technique to test for hypothesis. The chi-square test was established to know if there is relationship between removal of fuel subsidy income and livelihood. And to test if removal of subsidy have effect in Dutsin-Ma local Government, Nigeria. This is stated in this model as follows

3.5 Empirical model

The study used chi-square technique by using livelihood as the depending variable and removal of subsidy as the independent variable. Therefore the equation is stated as follows:

$$LLH = f(RFS)$$

Stated differently:

$$\sum LLH = \beta_0 \sum_n \beta_n RFS \text{ ----- (1)}$$

RFS = Removal of Fuel Subsidy. Where Insecurity can be disaggregated into, kidnapping, killing,

LLH = Income level

A priori expectation

The a priori expectation is that there is a significant relationship between removal of fuel subsidy, Livelihood and income in the study area.

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

Questionnaires were administered in the field for data collection and were summarized using descriptive and inferential statistics. Results of these analyses was presented in form of tables and simple percentage while chi-square test was used to test for the hypothesis. The test were conducted at 5% level of significance.

4.1 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This section examined the implications of removal of fuel subsidy on livelihood of households in Dutsin-Ma local government area, Nigeria. In addition, the test for hypothesis was conducted to see if removal of fuel subsidy affects livelihood hence the quality of life of households in Dutsin-Ma local government area.

4.1 Bio-Data of Respondents

Table 1: Bio-Data of Respondents showing their characteristics

Variable		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	226	57.8
	Female	165	42.2
	Total	391	100
Age	25 – 34 Years	99	25.3
	35 – 44 Years	92	23.5
	45 – 54 Years	125	32
	55 – 64 years	63	16.1

	65 and above	12	3.1
	Total	391	100
Marital Status	Single	78	19.9
	Married	238	72.4
	Divorced	11	2.8
	widow	19	4.9
	Total	391	100
Religion	Islam	313	80.6
	Christianity	77	19.2
	Others	01	0.2
	Total	391	100
Education Level	None	02	0.5
	Primary	49	12.5
	Secondary	241	61.6
	Tertiary	99	25.3
	Total	391	100
Occupation	Formal employment	123	31.5
	Self employed	104	26.6
	Farmer/Livestock rearing	105	26.9
	Casual/Temporary work	59	15
	Total	391	100
Family size	Below five children	163	41.7
	Above five children	228	58.3
	Total	391	100

Source: Field work 2025

Table 4.1 above presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents in the study. Regarding educational attainment, the majority of the respondents (61.6%) had attained a secondary level of education. Following this, 25.3% had a tertiary education, while 12.5% had only a primary education. Only 0.5% have no formal education. In terms of age distribution, the respondents that are within the 45 – 54 years comprise 32% of the sample. The age between 25 – 34 years constituted 25.3% only. Further more 23.5% are between 35 – 44 years, 16.1% are between 55 – 64 years, and only 3.1% are 65 years and above. Based on marital status, majority (72.4%) of the respondents were married, 19.9% are Single while widowers comprised of 4.9%. lastly only 2.8% are divorced. For religion the majority (80.8%) of the respondents are Muslims, and 19.2% are Christians. Looking at primary occupation, the largest segment of the respondents comprising of 31.5% were involved in formal employment. 26.9% are engaged

in farming/Livestock rearing 26.6% are self-employed. 15.1% of the respondents are casual/temporary workers. Finally, regarding family size, the distribution was relatively even, showing that majority (58.3%) have a family size of more than five members. and 41.7% have a family size of less than five members.

The implication of fuel subsidy removal on household income in Dutsin-Ma LGA

Table 4.2: Respondents response on loss of income since removal of fuel subsidy

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	186	47.6
No	205	52.4
	391	100

Source: Field work 2025

Table 4.2 reveals the response rate on loss of income since the removal of the fuel subsidy. The findings show that 47.6 indicated that they lost income while 52.4% indicated they did not loose any income. The implication is that most of the households indicated that they did not loose any income as a result of fuel subsidy removal.

Table 4.3: Respondents response on whether the removal of fuel subsidy affected their primary source of income

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Yes, positively	038	9.7
Yes, negatively	315	80.6
No impact	38	9.7
Total	391	100

Source: Field work 2025

Table 4.3 reveals the respondents' response rate on whether the fuel subsidy removal affected their primary source of income. The findings show that 80.6% indicated that it negatively affected that primary source of income, 9.7% responded that yes it positively affected and ther was no impact respectively. Therefore we conclude based on the majority (80.6%) that subsidy removal negatively affected the primary source of income of households in the study area.

Table 4.4: Respondents response Rate on the amount Households receive as Government Social Welfare Support

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Below ₦40,000	313	80.1
₦40,000-79,999	49	12.5

₦80,000-119,999	19	4.9
₦120,000 and above	10	2.6
Total	391	100

Source: Field work 2025

Table 4.4 presents data on the government financial aid or social welfare received by the surveyed households. The vast majority of the surveyed households reported receiving relatively small amounts of government financial aid or social welfare. Specifically, 80.1% of the households received below ₦40,000. 12.5% of the households received between ₦40,000 and ₦79,999, while 4.9% of the households received between ₦80,000 and ₦119,999. And lastly only 2.8% received ₦120,000 and above in government financial aid or social welfare.

4.5 Test of Hypothesis

This section analyzed the test of hypothesis using the chi-square test

H0: The removal of fuel subsidy has no impact on the livelihood of households in Dutsin-Ma LGA.

Table 4.5.1: Hypothesis Crosstabulation

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Has the removal of fuel subsidy affected your primary source of income? * Have you or any household member lost income since fuel subsidy removal?	390	99.7%	1	0.3%	391	100.0%

Sources: Researcher’s Computation using SPSS V22, 2025.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	85.138a	6	.000
Likelihood Ratio	99.686	6	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.000	1	.990
N of Valid Cases	390		

a. 6 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

Decision Rule

Accept H0 if $\chi^2_c < \chi^2_t$

Reject H0 if $\chi^2_c > \chi^2_t$

$\chi^2_c = 85.138$

$\alpha = 0.05$; since it is a two tail test we divide α by $2(\alpha/2) = 0.025$.

$df = 6$

$\chi^2_t = 14.449$

Table 4.5.1 shows the cross tabulation and chi-square test for hypothesis testing. The result revealed that χ^2_c (85.138) is greater than χ^2_t (14.449), therefore we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that fuel subsidy removal have impact on the livelihood of households in Dutsin-Ma local government area of Katsina state Nigeria. The findings is similar to Akerele (2024). The study found that the increase in oil prices due to the partial subsidy removal had adversely impacted various economic activities such as sales, production, and transportation, leading to decreased profitability in agriculturaure. It also aligned with the findings of Udoh, Iyoho, and Udo (2024) where they found that fuel price hikes following the subsidy removal exacerbated the cost of living, poverty, and inequality in Akwa Ibom communities. It also supported the findings of Umar and Mohd Nor's (2024) where they found that the subsidy removal negatively impacted income levels, savings, and access to basic needs, particularly among large families and less educated households.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Arising from the findings fuel subsidy revealed that, fuel subsidy removal contribute in the increase of expenditure on transportation, healthcare, education, energy and utilities. It also revealed that, the increase in the cost of essential services force the households to decrease expenditure on certain goods and services which in turn reduces their welfare. Thus, fuel subsidy is directly proportionate to the livelihood of households. The effect of fuel subsidy removal on the livelihood of the households in the study area, based on the findings is negative. Therefore the study recommends that Government should broader its social investment programs so as to reach as much as wider range of citizens, not some privilege ones. This can be done by enhancing health care services scheme. Health care services can mitigate and ameliorate the effect of removal of fuel subsidy. This also be done by government investing in the health care system. Secondly, government can support household income through promotion of entrepreneurship of households in addition to giving them grants to support them. This can be done through public private partnership to serve as counterpart funding to support the young entrepreneurs.

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STRATEGIC PLANNING FOR POPULATION GROWTH AND WEALTH CREATION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The population of a country is primarily resource based, which can be utilize for wealth creation. The paper employed qualitative research, involving published data. It stresses the need to utilize population growth for wealth creation, especially by tying it to productive ventures as practiced in China and India. It is apt that Nigeria population continues to grow but must be strategically tailored to create wealth in line with the unique nature of her economy. Population growth is not expected to be a hindrance to socioeconomic development of a nation but a catalyst for improvement, competencies, technical know-how and attainment of national goals. Unfortunately, this is not the case with Nigeria where population growth planning is not given top priority; and where national planning processes are tied to population projections since 2006. Indeed, the poor planning of population dynamics has disastrous implications which Nigeria is currently experiencing. While the developed nations invest heavily on planning for its population growth and reaping the benefits thereof, Nigeria is still grappling with the consequences of it, due to poor planning strategies. Therefore, the need for Nigeria to plan for a comprehensive census count taking and maximize her population structure and dynamics through designed policies and programme for wealth creation are suggested. [Word count: 207].

INTRODUCTION

The population of a country cannot be studied in isolation without linking it to wealth creation. The two concepts are interlinked, affecting each other in diverse ways. It is in this connection that the population policy of Nigeria reflect government plan to create wealth and provide social welfare for the citizens, using population knowledge. The 1988 population policy which was later revised in 2006 contains government position on these matters. For instance,

the 2006 national population policy which was tagged: National Policy on population for sustainable development contains wealth creation and social welfare packages for citizens.

Both the 1988 and 2006 population policies aimed at using awareness creation and population education to let the public know that provision of social welfare is tied to the population situation of the country. As a matter of fact, population processes and its dynamics influence wealth creation provisions. Example, the population structures and distributions of sex, age, occupation, marriage and geography determines where and how wealth are created and distributed. The synergy between population and wealth creation take into cognizance the knowledge of population structures and dynamics to reduce poverty and beeves up food security among the citizens (USAID, 2010).

The wealth creation programs of government are in most cases tied to housing, health, education, agriculture, food and security, economic, energy, environment, transportation, security, employment and social amenities. Wealth creation programs may be comprehensive to cover technical, financial, social and psychological dimensions, and each aspect has a desirable impact on national economy (Morgen et al, 2013). The primary purpose of wealth creation is to alleviate poverty and suffering among the citizenry. However, research had shown that wealth creation programs in most developing countries had no meaningful impact on those it was meant for due to ineffective coordination and corrupt practices (Olawaju et al, 2014).

It is noteworthy that countries with high population density such as China and India and the USA are competing as economic giants in the world. However, due to the inability to plan and utilize a given population dynamics for wealth creation, many countries, e.g., Nigeria is still grappling with poverty. Going by the 2006 population census, the Nigeria's population is 140 million with a total land area of 923,768 square kilometers (356,376 square miles) and a population density, estimated at 226 per KM² (586 people per square kilometer) (Ottong, 2006). Currently, the Worldometer of the United Nation's data put the total population of Nigeria in 2021 at 212,361,015 (Census News, 2022). By these figures, Nigeria is ranked as the largest population in Africa and 7th in the world (Census News, 2022). Nigeria population is equivalent to 2.64% of the total world population, with a median age of 18.1 years (United Nations, 2020).

It is the population that provides the means by which the wealth of a country is created, used and maximized. A population irrespective of her size can be developed and used for the benefit of both individuals and the society. The ability of a nation to harness necessary information, skills and resources to create wealth would map her out among comity of nations. Most developing nations have begun to realize the gains to be achieved by planning her population growth rate ((Oluwatayo, 2009; Ottor, 2012). A planned population growth rate enhances competitiveness, innovations, creativity and flexibility. It also creates opportunities and improvements in living conditions and strengthens the economic foundations of a nation. Ottong (2006) asserts that it is cost effective to plan for population growth rate of a country; especially if it's structured for wealth creation. In modern societies, population growth is subjected to strategic planning; and in accordance with the population needs of a nation.

Concept of population

Population is the general term that refers to the number of humans, animal, things and place found in a geographical area at a particular period (Ushie & Isokon, 2019). However in the context of this paper, our focus is on human population, which implies the total number of

people including males and females of all categories residing in a determined geographical area at a particular period of time (Akinfeleye et al, 2014). The study of human population is essentially linked to the well-being of man and the society. In other words, it is meant to address the socioeconomic development of the society. A country's population is usually a consequence of the interplay of birth, deaths and migration processes. When the birth rate is higher than the death rate or when the in-migration (coming in) is higher than the emigration (going outside), the population tend to rise but would fall if the reverse is the case (Okumnadewas, 2006).

Consequences of Over Population

Over population infers that the number of people in an area is above the carrying capacity of available resources, and therefore such an area would definitely experience the yoke of population pressures (William et al., 2009). More often the population growth rate causes a change or affects the living standard of a people or society. For example, Thomas Malthus in 1798 pointed out that a rapidly increasing population without a corresponding increase in resources will be a threat to human existence. This implies that if the available resources are inadequate to support a high population, the population is bound to face unmitigated challenges.

The pressures usually experienced from over population may be in the form of environmental challenges such as reckless exploitation of resources and environmental instability, communal land conflicts and over exploitation of cultivated land as well as impoverishment (Holiday, 2007). Indeed, an uncontrolled population growth rate would affect the socioeconomic development of a country. It is also on point that countries with high populations experience more of the effects of climate change than others (Edward & Ngaji, 2010). Animashaun (2012) also argued that a high population usually induces a "high demand for food, shelter, clothing and other life supporting needs derived directly or indirectly from the natural environment".

High populations especially the ones in urban centers generates urban wastes and pollution (Faniran & Ojo, 2000).

Indicators of High Population

The demographic processes of birth, death and migration interlink to determine population dynamics in a country. In other words, the population change, size or growth rates are the consequences of the processes of birth, death and migration. When the birth rate is in excess of the death rate, an increase in population occurs but if the death rate is in excess of the death rate, population decrease happens (Ushie & Isokon, 2019). In the same vein, if the entry of people into a country (in migration) supersede the number that goes out (out migration) the population will also increase, but the reverse is the case if those that goes out (out migration) are more than those that comes in (in migration).

Concept of Wealth Creation

Wealth creation is a process involving investments aim at generating a source of income that will meet human needs or aspirations. Therefore, wealth creation encompasses investment and gain in wealth. The wealth creation process starts with goal setting and ends with goal attainment. The wealth creation process also entails earning higher growth for the future. In other words, the wealth creation process is planned for a safe and secure livelihood in the future

(Sannihitha, 2021). Wealth creation goals are defined based on the time period. These might be short term goals, medium term goals or long term goals. Short term goals may last between 1-3 years. Medium term goals may last between 3-5 years while long term goals last from five years and above (Macunovich, 2016). Investment opportunities available for wealth creation for a country like Nigeria include population resources such as population structure and distribution. Others are potential investments and mutual funding.

Investments towards wealth creation take many forms. A few examples include: investments in equities, interest or dividends and mutual funds. Wealth creation may as well be tangible or intangible. The tangibility of wealth creation has multidimensional dimensions including mineral resources, infrastructural development such as health care, schools, roads, and pipe borne water. The intangible dimensions include skills, knowledge, and practice as well as planned experience for improved performance among others.

A population based investment is the surest way to wealth creation. In every human population, are found persons with goals and dreams and those that plan about the future. If Nigeria can build up her human resources and use them at a time to create wealth, the country would have achieved utmost development. To do so, the government should start investing on the citizenry. It requires the planned effort of government to provide infrastructural facilities for wealth creation. Investing in education, health care, social amenities among others will help in wealth creation.

Utilization of Population Structure for Wealth Creation

The population structure and dynamics are of vital importance for wealth creation and nation building. Devey (2009) stated that every population has potentials which can be developed and utilized for the benefit of her citizenry. A country with high population density for example may take advantage of her population size to command international patronage and support in her area of interest. Within the population structure of a country are to be tapped the necessary information and skills for tasks executions in unique ways. High population in any country can therefore be used to harness and develop a country's resources for its continuous growth and advancement (Mkpong, 2008). According to Isokon and Onyema (2015) the population of any country should be strategically organized towards improving the well-being of the people in the country. High population if properly utilized is expected to be a catalyst for improving competencies, technical know-how and perhaps enable the country attain her height.

The international communities have begun to realize the gains to be achieved from high population density. A country with a high population presents opportunities for increased creativity and exploitation of resources. Supporting this view, Agbam (2019) argued that high population is a resource based enterprise which if properly managed could promote innovation and enhance creativity, flexibility and competitiveness. It also helps in adapting and facilitating the application of new approaches to doing things. High population density also brings about higher earnings, promotion opportunities, and improvements in working and living conditions and strengthening the general economic foundations of the people (Agbam, 2019).

Ottong (2006) also asserts that high population density is beneficial when it is planned and structured for service delivery. A country with high population density is expected to map out strategic plans towards developing skills and competencies in all areas of human endeavors. Unfortunately, this has not the case with most countries with high population densities, and

where the high population status is mainly considered as a burden. Countries like China and India have become leading economies in the world as a result of the proper utilization of their population status as the largest and second largest populations in the world respectively. Thus, these countries utilize their number to attain economic heights in the comity of nations.

Recently, the Global Trends in Population and Human Development (2020) reported that Spain appointed a Minister for Sex to oversee how the falling birth rate of the country could rise. This is on the wake of impending population crisis, where the population is declining rapidly instead of increasing. According to the Global Trends in Population and Human Development (2020), the number of childless couples tripled from 1.5 million in 1977 to 4.4 million in 2015. With the appointment of Barreira as the country's tsar and the new population policy, it is expected that Spanish women had to produce 1.3 children well below the EU figure of 1.58 (Global Trends in Population and Human Development, 2020). It is a recognized fact that high population is a critical factor for economic and social development of any nation as it determines the standard of living of the citizens. When a country for example, has a highly and viable population with expertise and skilled hands, it is moved to position itself to maximally create wealth to sustain the population.

It is also observed that high population in a country enhances job creation and coordination of production and services, acquisition of skills, among others. The implication of this is that proper and effective utilization of the potentials of such a population is significant for wealth creation. The essence of a high productive population is therefore to create and maximize the skills of citizenry and in so doing achieve greater production efficiency in wealth creation. Thus, Ekpenyong (2013) opined that when a population is high and productive, its capacity to adopt new technologies and methods of doing things increases. Because high populations is usually characterized by stiff competitions and rivalry, especially if the population is heterogeneous, the citizenry would adapt easily to changing environmental conditions, thereby enhancing their chances of survival by the creation of wealth of diverse dimensions.

Unfortunately, most countries with high population, particularly third world countries have not been able to adapt to the complexity of their numbers and also utilize it for wealth creation. For example, Nigeria is known to be the giant of Africa, primarily because of its high population, indeed the largest in Africa, yet rated as the third poorest country in Africa and the 46 in the world (Owuamanam & Alowolodu, 2010). Some countries are poor today because of the absence of adequate population to tap the available resources in the country. It is also generally observed that most third world countries pay little or no attention to the utilization of her population size and turning its fortune to a productive population. Even, when a population is high, it is less productive, because much of the human and material resources are not tapped and plunged in profitable ventures.

In some countries, the population has been drastically misdirected and misused by the leadership or the elite class with concomitant wastage, corrupt practices, and civil unrest among others. Also, in spite of the importance of a country being highly populated, most populated countries do not have any laid down population policy that addresses the key challenges caused by over population in order to promote and enhance the well-being of the populace. Where there's a population policy at all, it is poorly or not implemented. In most cases, the population policy only favors the elite class with little or no provision made for the masses, thus making

them impoverished, and exhibit symptoms such as frustration indicated by loss of productivity and retarded development.

Scholars have long discovered that population growth rate and the resources in any society are interdependently linked and can therefore be used to improve the standard of living of the people in that society (Adejuwon, 2015). Both the population growth rate and the resources in an area are meant to be exploited and utilized for the well-being of the people. According to Ayuk (2012) the rate of population growth can be planned and controlled in line with the processes of social and technological changes to bring about socioeconomic development. For example, China and India being the first and second largest populated countries in the world respectively have demonstrated this feat by using population as a resource base with scientific and technological innovations to create wealth, thereby changing the narratives of the people. The high population of a country can be maximized to generate wealth through policies and programs involving skill acquisition, adequate provision of social welfare packages (e.g., payment of pensions, gratuity, health care and infrastructural development).

Nigeria is experiencing high population growth rate with a greater percentage of the citizenry living below the poverty line due to her inability to have a viable and workable population policy and programs (Hirschman, 2011). It is also on record that Nigeria's population growth rate is experiencing a modest economic growth rate as a result of lack of identifiable population indices or data to work with, poor planning methods and population implementation failures. To this end, Hirschman (2011) recommended that a country with a high population usually have socioeconomic challenges and can be addressed by the creation of jobs and values. He added that such a country needs to increase her productivity in all her economic value chains, and paying special attention to women, children and youths. Hirschman (2011) further suggested that a country with a high population should formulate policies that facilitate innovative ideas and initiate programs that would generate meaningful opportunities for the youths. On his part, May (2000) posited that exclusive economic growth is required to solve the problems associated with a high populations. In a highly populated country, appropriate interventions such as job creations and employment opportunities are needed to be given consideration as a way of cushioning the effects of unhealthy competitions and unemployment arising from the high population.

Preston (2017) maintained that sustainable job and wealth creations can be generated from a population that is maximally high, and is planned to develop key sectors of the economy as well as the infrastructure. In a highly populated country, the key drivers of development and wealth creation include productive enterprises that contribute to national GDP, as well as the development of social infrastructures such as health, education, transportation, energy, public-sector service and finance among others (African Politeia Institute, 2020).

According to Ajuwon (2015) a population is said to have created wealth or has increasing wealth potentials when certain features are observed. Ajuwon (2015) noted that a rise in the living standard of the people coupled with the high demand for goods and services are clear indicators. Other indicators include increasing investment opportunities, high level of socioeconomic activities such as infrastructural expansions, scientific and technological innovations and inventions, as well as the springing up of new businesses. Besides, the population would continue to grow moderately due to quality health care. Also, to be noticed

are environmental and noise pollution, and high level competitions in virtually all aspects of human enterprises (Ajuwon, 2015).

Components of the population structure that create wealth

Also, the structure and pattern of distribution of a population determines to a large extent the capacity of a population to create wealth. Because, the structure and distribution of the population is significant in the analysis of socioeconomic development, demographers have identified components of the population structure namely the sex, age and marriage as having significant impact on wealth creation.

Sex structure and distribution of the population:

The proportion of males and female populations and their respective needs has always been a part of budget proposals and planning of many nations. According to Ajuwon (2015) the US government budgeted US\$35 trillion for the well-being and sustenance of women and children in the year 2018 alone. The sex structure and distribution of the population also help the government and the society to plan for the resource needs of each group. It may be assumed that a country with more female population which is sometimes attributed to a matrilineal decent or root, have the capacity to create more of feminist related wealth such as sewing, cooking, and washing. After all, empirical sociological literature have revealed that men are instrumentalist having the passion to engage in hard and challenging tasks unlike the females who are permissive and given to doing light and simple tasks (Adeyemi, 2011). In the same vein, societies with more males will be involved in male related tasks like carpentry, mechanics, felling of woods, and engineering.

Age structure and distribution of the population:

The age structure and distribution of the population is a veritable tool for wealth creation. Age structure of a population comprises various age groups. From demographic perspectives, the age structure is examined under three categories:

Persons below 15 years of age (e.g. Infant and children);

Persons between 15 and 65 years (e.g. young or working population)

Persons from 65 years and above (e.g. older or aged).

A population with a greater percentage of infant, children and the aged or older persons is described as dependent population, while a population with young people is termed productive age, active population or working population. Any society populated or dominated by the dependent population will suffer from poverty, destitution and scarcity of resources. This type of population is unhealthy to a nation's survival and socioeconomic development. The standard of living would equally become low, as both savings and investments would reduce drastically. Most of the demands for goods and services would be tailored towards the needs of older people even as government expenditures on pensions and retirement benefits, provision of health care for the old people would be high compared to the provisions made towards the needs of the younger generation (Ushie & Isokon, 2019).

On the other hand, a society with a dominant, productive or working population has the leverage to create wealth. This type of population is innovative and skillful in capital formations and investments and ready to take risks. In a bid to cater for the educational, health and social

needs of the dependent population, they work hard to create more wealth and to make life comfortable for all.

Geographical distribution of the population:

Some societies such as cities and urban areas contain high population densities which favors wealth creation than some areas with low population density. For example, places like the dry Savannah regions where the ecological conditions are unfavorable, do not attract high population, and therefore lack the capacity and resources to create wealth. The urban areas with high population density usually attract government strategic planning and provision of infrastructural and social amenities which in turn facilitates wealth creation. Also, areas with abundant resources such as mineral deposits, fertile land, mines, and oil exploration are usually populated by people who in turn tap the resources in the area to create wealth.

Occupational distribution of the population:

The type of occupation or vocation common or dominate an area could determine and enhance wealth creation. A situation where a greater percentage of youths are unemployed, wealth creation tends to be a fruitless venture. Rather the youths will be involved in destructive and restive behaviors, indulge in drugs and alcoholism, criminality and other unwholesome behaviors. But where employment opportunities abound and the ratio of youth employment is high, many people would earn a living; and as many are engaged in manufacturing industry, mining, public service, private sector, agriculture, arts and music, wealth is simultaneously created (Adeyemi, 2011).

Marriage and family structure:

We have different forms of marriages and family structures such as monogamy, polygamy, and polyandry. In some marriages, the woman stays in the house as a house wife while the man is the working type and fends for the family. But in most other marriages both the man and the woman are workers and jointly fend for the household. Some societies or cultures encourage her citizenry to work irrespective of their marital status. For example, in the developed world, marriage is not a barrier to any person whether man or woman to contribute to the socioeconomic development of the society vis-a-vis in wealth creation. However, in most third world countries, women are relegated to second class citizens, denied right of property ownership while in most rural communities, the girl child is denied the right to attend school. Consequently, women are handicapped to be engaged in wealth creation.

Migration processes:

The migration processes has significant impact on wealth creation capacity of a country. For example, the massive movement of young and talented individuals out of their country to foreign lands in search of greener pastures causes brain drain syndrome. The implications are that brain drain helps to transfer the wealth of a nation to other countries. Conversely, many migrants into a country are diplomats, investors and tourists who may help to boost the wealth creation abilities of a host country. The significant contributions of multinational corporations and foreign expertise towards scientific and technological developments in Nigeria are perfect examples.

Socio - Demographic Factors Influencing Wealth Creation

Availability and accessibility of human and natural resources:

A country with mineral deposits, technical know-how, modern technological infrastructures and agricultural production capacities would stimulate wealth creation. In China for example, where there are so many industries, good transportation system and employment opportunities the wealth creation capabilities are high. Similarly, a country with social infrastructures, and adequate social amenities, such as good transportation system, pipe borne water supply, power supply, schools, and health facilities attract capacities for wealth creation.

Climatic conditions:

Favorable climatic conditions like adequate rainfall, relief, temperature, fertile soil, friendly weather attracts wealth creation capabilities; but where the climatic conditions are harsh, unfriendly and rugged, the zeal to work for and create wealth would be low if not dead.

Political stability:

The wealth of a country and her citizenry is dependent on the relative political stability and peace. People cherish peace and security of a place which the government can provide. Developed countries like Britain, USA, and Mexico are known for their tight security networks and stable and peaceful environment which attracts investors and multiple businesses in these countries. African countries are poor and impoverished due to the political instability and security challenges posed by insurgencies.

Theoretical Framework

The Neoclassical growth model by Alfred Marshal (1970) was adopted in the analysis of effective planning of population growth and wealth creation in Nigeria. The model is an attempt to modify Neo-Malthusian theory. The model assumed those demographic indices such as population structure and household size influences household or family income and behavior. It also assumed that reproducible capital, fixed factors such as land and natural resources, advantages of scale and population size in general influences economic and social welfare. It further assumed that age-distributed population influences level of savings and optimal life cycle consumption among household members (Lee, 1993). For instance, if there is high fertility or increase in family size, household resources available for saving and investment will reduce. On the other hand, if there is low fertility or decrease in family size, household resources available for saving and investment will become high.

It further implies that the proportion of the working age in the population will rise and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per head of the household members will also rise, if the number of children per household is less or reduces (Brander & Dowrick, 1990). According to Cootz (1979) capital accumulation which is essential for labor is also determined by the household size. Example, a large household size will discourage accumulation of capital. Also, the rate of wages paid or to be paid is dependent on the size of the household. This suggests that when the size of the household is large, the wages will be low and when it is small, disposable wages will be high. The model further considers the linkages underlying labor markets, household sizes and fixed factors such as land. It assumed that since the land is a fixed factor, a large household

(labor) on the fixed land will result to the fertility of the soil and the yield to suffer diminishing returns, which in turn will lead to poor yield, low incomes and a very low standard of living for the people.

The Neo-classical growth model is relevant to effective planning of population growth rate and wealth creation in Nigeria. The rate of population (household size) is usually measured against available resources. A household (population) without a considerable resource, e.g. land as fixed factor to sustain it will lead to impoverishment. This type of a household rarely creates wealth. Conversely, a household (population) with sufficient resources e.g. land as fixed factor is assumed to have the capacity to create wealth. It is notable that if the population of a country is high and continue to increase at rapid rates above the carrying capacity of available resources, wealth creation will not be feasible. In Nigeria for example, her high population growth rate without proper utilization of available resources, and low savings and investment levels, makes her wealth creation goal difficult to achieve. The model also laid claim to the fact that wealth creation will invariably increase or expand the size of population (leading to high population). This, in the long run will result to diminishing return setting in, since land and landed resources are fixed factors.

The Neo-classical growth model has some limitations such as its abstraction from technological changes. To some extent, the burdens of large family sizes can be diluted by new investments and methods of production, capital formation and out-migration processes, among others. Secondly, the model tends to offer a universal approach in the interpretation of population phenomenon and development. This position is risky because it does not take into account the peculiarities and relativity of cultures, peoples and countries. Furthermore, size of household cannot be completely predicted by economic reasons alone. There is need for social implications in economic rationalization, premised on the need to understand and interpret local models as determinants of behavior, rather than imposing universal economics models of the universal “economic person” on all cultural settings.

Recommendations / Conclusion

The creation of wealth in any country must recognize the significant role of the population structure and distribution. When once this is done right, it is easy to discover the resources in each population structure that can be relevant for wealth creation. Disciplined leadership and political will power are the keys to mobilize the components of a population towards creating wealth. If countries like China and India for example can take advantage of the power of her high population status and attain economic heights and high level of political stability, Nigeria with the highest population in Africa need to do something about it. There is no doubt that Nigeria has numerous investment opportunities spread across the country, it is essential to deal with her diversity challenges such as ethnicity, religious diversity and ethnocentrism; and instead work in unity of purpose and unity in diversity in wealth creation.

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